

Transforming Justice: The Jurisprudence of Restorative Justice for Victims of Crime in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of restorative justice within the context of Nigeria's criminal justice system, with a view to addressing the transformation of justice, taking into cognisance the needs and interests of victims of crime. It examines retributive justice in Nigeria, focusing on its implications for victims of crime. The longstanding tradition of retributive justice in Nigeria has been fraught with challenges, often neglecting the needs and rights of victims. It addresses the needs of crime victims in Nigeria from the jurisprudence of restorative justice framework perspective. The primary purpose of this research is to analyse how retributive justice can be transformed to serve victims within the Nigerian legal context. Using a qualitative methodology that includes a review of legal texts, interviews with legal practitioners, victims of crime, and policymakers, this study identifies key gaps in the current justice framework. The findings reveal that while retributive justice aims to hold offenders accountable, it frequently fails to address victims' needs for restitution, closure, and engagement in the justice process. Consequently, the paper argues for a paradigm shift towards a more integrated approach that harmonises retributive principles with restorative practices. The conclusions emphasise the necessity of reforming Nigeria's justice system to prioritise victims' rights, thereby enhancing the overall legitimacy and effectiveness of legal proceedings. This research contributes to the discourse on justice reform in Nigeria, advocating for a model that acknowledges the multifaceted impacts of crime and the importance of victim participation in the pursuit of justice.

Keywords: *Jurisprudence, Restorative Justice, Retributive Justice, Nigeria, Victim*

Introduction: Restorative justice can be said to have its roots not only in Western conceptions but also in non-Western traditions. Llewellyn and Howse argue that a shift towards a restorative model of justice can be best understood as a return to the roots of justice, rather than as a new age approach for an ailing criminal justice system.¹ In contemporary societies, the justice system leans heavily on the pillars of punitive measures. These punitive measures could be short-term or long-term measures. Despite the measures, the justice system often falls short of addressing the underlying issues.² The historical conception of restorative justice is not limited to Western practices but also includes some interesting history in the lasting traditions of the indigenous Africans. Stout is of the opinion that most of what is claimed to be traditional African justice is based upon anecdotal, unsustainable claims.³ The very idea of African customary law is considered an oxymoron by Western writers and it is their belief that African law is not law *per se*, but primitive practices which predate law.⁴ In the same vein, it has been argued that to ‘describe the indigenous criminal justice as necessarily restorative is to romanticise the past and to provide an excuse for re-colonising indigenous groups’.⁵

In Nigeria, crimes are committed daily and the Nigerian laws for a long period of time have centred upon prescribing punishments for the offenders. This article is aimed at appraising the jurisprudence of restorative justice to victims of crime under the present criminal justice system with a view to ascertaining and restoring the victims of crime to their status quo ante.

¹ Llewellyn, JJ & Howse, R, *Restorative Justice: A conceptual framework*, Canada: Law Commission, 1999 as cited in Tauri, J, The Plastic Shamans of Restorative Justice, The Routledge International Handbook on Decolonizing Justice, 2023, <<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/76004/restricted-resource?bitstreamId=1b2f96e3-4a70-45c9-b116-29aa1a08fd6d#page=74>>.

² Umbreit, MS, Vos, B, & Coates, L, *Restorative Justice in The Twenty-First Century: A Social Movement Full of Opportunities and Pitfalls*. Marquette Law Review, 89, 251-304, 2005 as cited in Patel, S, *Embedded Healthcare Policing*, (Embedded healthcare policing, 2022), <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/uclalr69&div=20&id=&page=>>>.

³ Stout, B, *Restorative Justice in South Africa: Resolving Conflict*, British Journal of Community Justice Vol.1(3) pp 51-61, 2003.

⁴ Costa, A, *The Myth of Customary Law*, South African Journal of Human Rights 14 (4):525-538, 1998 as cited in Olwage, E, *Under the Leadwood Tree: Disputing Land, Mobility and Belonging in Post-Colonial Southern Kaoko*, <<https://kups.ub.uni-koeln.de/61786/>>.

⁵ Daly, K, *Restorative Justice: The Real Story*, 2017 as cited in Marder, ID, Mapping Restorative Justice and Restorative Practices in Criminal Justice in the Republic of Ireland, International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice, 2022, Volume 70, <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1756061622000222>>.

The jurisprudence of restorative justice to the victims of crime in Nigeria

The word “jurisprudence” is derived from the Latin term *juris prudentia*, which means “the study, knowledge or science of law.”⁶ The term “jurisprudence” is also used alternatively as ‘legal theory and/or “philosophy of law.”⁷ Jurisprudence is the study and theory of law. Scholars of the concept are also known as jurists or legal theorists and they hope to obtain a deeper understanding of the nature of law, of legal reasoning, legal systems and from the colonial era to date, has always been prescribing punishments to the offenders of crime with the sole aim of protecting the interest of the offenders and the State alone, leaving out the victims of crime to wallow in the excruciating pains caused as a result of the crime. The Criminal Code Act and the Penal Code Act focus mainly on punishing the offenders of crime while the Criminal Procedure Act and the Criminal Procedure Code state the procedures to be adopted for the punishment of the offenders in the Southern part of Nigeria and the Northern part of Nigeria respectively. The efforts of all stakeholders, including the courts, the public prosecution unit of government and the law enforcement agencies are mutually complimentary towards the protection of the offender and the State’s interests, while that of the victim is abandoned, neglected and treated as not important in retributive criminal justice system.

This is supported by various legal frameworks and case law that advocate for the rights and restoration of victims. In Nigeria, the legal framework supporting restorative justice includes, *inter alia* the Administration of Criminal Justice Act, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act, etc.

⁶ Hart H. *The Concept of Law*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1982 as cited in Bogdandy, AV, Principles of a Systemic Deficiencies Doctrine: How to Protect Checks and Balances in the Member States. *Common Market Law Review*, 2020, Volume 57, Issue 3, pp. 705-740, <<https://doi.org/10.54648/cola2020690>>.

⁷Elegido, JM, *Jurisprudence*, Spectrum Law Pub., 1994, <https://books.google.com.ng/books/about/Jurisprudence.html?id=3z0anQAACAAJ&redir_esc=y>.

The features of restorative justice under the Administration of Criminal Justice Act are reviewed as follows:

Plea Bargain

The ACJA introduces the concept of plea bargain which is a negotiated agreement between a prosecutor and a criminal defendant whereby the defendant pleads guilty to a lesser offence or to one of multiple charges in exchange for some concession by the prosecutor, usually, a more lenient sentence or a dismissal of the other charges.⁸ Plea bargain is expressly authorised in statutes of the Nigerian criminal justice system. The first legislation that introduced and localised the concept of plea bargain agreement into Nigeria's criminal jurisprudence was the Administration of Criminal Justice Law of Lagos State, 2015. Plea bargain is the process whereby a criminal defendant and prosecutor reach a mutually satisfactory disposition of a criminal case, subject to court approval. In *Gava Corp. Ltd. v. F.R.N.*,⁹ the court held that when plea bargaining is successful, it results in a plea agreement between the prosecutor and defendant whereby the prosecutor agrees to dismiss certain charges or make favourable sentence recommendations to the court. Accordingly, plea bargain can conclude a criminal case without a trial.

The Court in the case of *Gava Corp. Ltd.* also held that by virtue of sections 75 and 76(4) of the law, notwithstanding in any contrary provision in the law, the Attorney-General of the State shall have the power to concede and accept a plea bargain from a person charged with any offence where the Attorney-General is of the view that the acceptance of such plea bargain is in the public interest, in the interest of justice (*ex debito justitiae*) and the need to prevent abuse of legal process.

The question is 'How restorative is a plea bargain under the Administration of Criminal Justice Act?' Though the plea bargain provisions under the ACJA offer some potential for restorative outcomes, they are not inherently designed as restorative practices. The effectiveness of the plea bargain as a restorative tool largely depends on how it is implemented, particularly concerning the victim's involvement and addressing the harm caused by the crime. For plea bargaining to be truly restorative within the Nigerian context, the provisions of the Act should be directly beneficial to the individual victim and community.

⁸ Section 75(1), Administration of Criminal Justice Law of Lagos State, 2015.

⁹ (2019) 10 N.W.L.R. (Pt. 1679) p. 139 at 143.

Compensatory Damages

Another feature of restorative justice under ACJA is that it provides a plaintiff with the amount necessary to replace what was lost, and nothing more. Thus, it covers the loss the innocent party incurred as a result of the breach of contract and the amount awarded is intended to make good or replace the loss caused by the breach. This is based on the principle of *restitutio in integrum*.

However, where the offender has not attained the age of 18 years and it appears to the court that the parent or guardian of the defendant conduces to the commission of the offence, the parent or guardian of the defendant shall pay the damages and costs. This thus means that monetary consideration thereof would serve as compensation to the victim of crime to restore him to *status quo ante*.

It should be noted that the general and special damages awarded by the Court are forms of compensatory damages. They are compensatory damages for harm that results from the wrong for which a party has sued. The general damages are monetary recovery in a lawsuit for injuries suffered, such as suffering, inability to perform certain functions, opportunity cost and/or breach of contract for which there is no exact monetary value that can be calculated. Usually, the harm is reasonably expected and need not be alleged or proved.

In *Mekwunye v. Emirates Airlines*¹⁰ the Court held that general damages are damages that the law presumes and they flow from the type of wrong complained about by the victim, i.e. the plaintiff. General damages are distinct from special damages, which are specific costs. While general damages are pecuniary compensation for injuries that follow the initial injury for which compensation is sought, specific damages involve economic losses such as loss of earnings, property damage and medical expenses. Both special damages and general damages constitute compensatory damages. Though the law is against double jeopardy in the form of compensations, the courts do award both general and special damages in deserving situations.

In the case of *Nwude v. FRN & Ors*,¹¹ the appellant argued that, having been sentenced to a term of imprisonment, it would be absurd to award compensatory damages to the respondent as that would amount to subjecting him to double jeopardy. The Court of Appeal held *inter alia* that a

¹⁰ (2019) 9 N.W.L.R. (Pt. 1677) p. 191 at 203.

¹¹ (2015) LPELR-25858 (CA)

sentencing to a term of years and/or with an order of forfeiture does not amount to double jeopardy because section 11 of the Advanced Fee Fraud Act provides that in addition to any other penalty prescribed under this Act, the High Court shall order a person convicted of an offence under this Act to make restitution to the victim of the false pretence or fraud by directing that person to pay to the victim an amount equivalent to the loss sustained by the victim. This section is not only about forfeiture, but also about compensation to the victim other than the Federal Government.

The exemplary damages, though sometimes referred to as punitive or vindictive damages, apply only where the conduct of the defendant is wanton and merits punishment. In *Mekwunye v. Emirates Airlines*, the court held that the defendant's conduct is considered to be wanton where it discloses fraud, malice, cruelty, insolence or the like, or where the conduct is a contumelious disregard of the plaintiff's rights.

The Jurisprudence of Restorative Justice to the Victims of Crime

The jurisprudence of restorative justice is increasingly recognised as a vital component of the criminal justice system, aiming to address the needs of victims and contribute to the rehabilitation of offenders. The jurisprudence of restorative justice in Nigeria is still developing and faces significant challenges in implementation. Currently, it is largely seen as inadequate, functioning primarily as bureaucratic paperwork rather than a robust alternative to traditional criminal justice processes. In other words, the practice of restorative justice in Nigeria is still in its early stages and has many challenges. It is often viewed as insufficient, mainly involving bureaucratic tasks instead of being a strong alternative to the usual criminal justice system which the conventional criminal justice system struggles to detach itself from as it is being practiced to date in most Nigerian courts. In Nigeria, restorative justice is supported by various domestic laws that align with international frameworks. The focus of restorative justice in Nigeria involves redressing the harm caused to victims while holding offenders accountable, aligning with broader international objectives to create a more balanced and humane criminal justice system. In other words, the Nigerian concept of restorative justice is supported by local laws that match international standards. This aims to repair the harm done to victims while also holding offenders responsible, fitting into global efforts to establish a fair and compassionate criminal justice system.

The fact that the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) Act provides that the proceeds of crime in financial crime cases be confiscated and forfeited to the Federal Government of Nigeria¹² does not in itself depict restorative justice to the victims of crime but to the Federal Government. Also that the provisions of the Administration of Criminal Justice Act (ACJA), to some extent, provide for restoration to the victims of crime, does not confirm that Nigeria's criminal justice system has in its entirety, embraced restorative criminal justice.

The jurisprudence of restorative justice to victims of crime under the present criminal justice system, is to ascertain the extent to which restorative justice can be applied to victims of crimes in Nigeria. Since the majority of role players in the administration of criminal justice in Nigeria are products of an adversarial system, one should not be surprised that the quality of criminal justice emanating from the regular Nigerian courts still broadly depict the negative consequences of the utilitarian approach to criminal justice.

Though the indigenous Nigerian legal system was basically conciliatory in character and restorative in nature, none of the punishments mentioned in both the Criminal Code Act¹³ and the Penal Code Act¹⁴ could be said to have the interest of the victim as its main focus.

Theories of Criminal Justice

The theories of criminal justice constitute the branch of philosophy of law that deals with criminal justice and in particular, punishment as the life of criminal law begins with criminalisation.¹⁵ Every crime and its punishment are defined by law which determines whether justice has been done or not. However, two theories of criminal justice shall be discussed as follows:

Theory of Retributive Justice: This theory posits that everyone who commits crime should suffer punishment as a deserved consequence of their condemnable act. The theory however, submits that punishments should cause enough pain to outweigh the pleasure derived from committing a

¹² Section 21, EFCC ACT, 2004,

¹³ Section 17, Criminal Code Cap. C38 Laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004 mentions death, imprisonment, whipping, fine and forfeiture as punishments under the Criminal Code.

¹⁴ Section 68, Penal Code Act, Cap. 89, Laws of Northern Nigeria, 1963 prescribed similar punishments like that of the Criminal Code.

¹⁵ Edwards J. *Theories of Criminal Law*, 2018, available at <<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/criminal-law/?o=600605&l=dir&qsrc=990&qo=contentPageRelatedSearch&ad=dirN>>.

crime. A competent court of jurisdiction shall administer this punishment and it must be in proportion to the harm occasioned by the crime as prescribed and proscribed under the relevant law.

Defiance Theory: Defiance theory suggests that fairness and legitimacy of experienced punishment are essential for the acknowledgement of shame, which conditions deterrence. If an offender feels that they are treated unfairly or that a sanction is illegitimate, they are more likely to defy the law and continue to offend. When punishment is perceived as unjust by the offender, it can lead to unacknowledged shame and defiant pride that increase the chance of engaging in future crime. Defiance theory combines re-integrative shaming, the sociology of master emotions, and compliance and procedural justice to explain how increased future offending against the sanctioning agent may result from how they reacted to the sanction.

Criminal exploitation is woven around procedural justice, re-integrative shaming and unacknowledged shame into an integrated theory of defiance.¹⁶

Theory of Penology: The body of law dealing with offences which may result in imposition of punishment, such as fine or imprisonment is known as criminal justice. Every society, in the quest to do justice, has to define its basis for imposition of punishment upon those who violate its tenets and norms. This led to the development of different theories of punishment in most legal systems, a combination of these theories form the basis for their penology. The theories of punishment are discussed as follows:

Theory of Restorative Justice: This theory emphasizes the utility of repairing the harm caused by criminal conduct. In this process, all stakeholders, including the public prosecution unit of government, the courts and law enforcement agencies, must cooperate in mutually complementary activities to accomplish the purpose of restorative justice. It is believed that the acts or practices reflective of restoration will respond to crime by taking steps to repair the harm caused by the crime. The process of achieving restorative justice must involve all stakeholders, and the outcome of the process will transform the relationship between communities and the government in

¹⁶ Zehr, H, *A Restorative Lens*, Restorative Justice, 2015 - taylorfrancis.com <<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315264868-3/restorative-lens-howard-zehr>>, as cited in Procter-Legg, T, Practitioner perspectives on a restorative community: An inductive evaluative study of conceptual, pedagogical, and routine practice, Laws, 2021,

preventing the future commission of crime by the offenders. The efficacy of restorative justice is based on the cumulative effect of the shame brought on the offender and the restoration of the victim, which leads to the reintegration of the offender into society has endeared restorative justice to the criminal justice administrators.¹⁷

Theory of Transformative Justice: This theory decries the perspective that crime is defined and framed by the State through the criminal justice system contrary to the position of retributive criminal justice system. This theory posits that the criminal justice system is essentially unjust as it disconnects victims from offenders by leaving the victim to suffer harm from criminal act without restitution. The theory postulates that the State control of criminal justice administration which is based on retributive justice, perpetuates injustice not only against the victims but also against the offender. In effect, transformative justice also referred to as rehabilitative justice considers the offender as an individual in need of treatment on account of the harm suffered and its attendant challenges. Thus, the theory of transformation justice submits that rather than considering victims and offenders as distinct entities, it should be reasoned that an offender may have caused harm and suffered harm all the same.

The structural approach in transformative justice strive to improve the quality of life of not only the victim but also the offender and the community by examining the root causes of crime. The theory of transformative justice overreached the offender-victim perspective emphasised and supported by restorative justice regime.

Utilitarian Theory: The Utilitarian effect of punishment extends to the punishment having a deterrent effect. In this regard, imposition of punishment and its painful effect on the offender deters the offender from continuing with a life of crime. It is not only the actual offender that is deterred from entering or continuing with a career of crime, other prospective offenders are also deterred as a result of the pain of punishment for crimes. Crimes of passion, which are committed without pre-planning or which are predicated on a spur-of-the-moment action or reaction, cannot be restrained by a deterrent punishment. Thus, deterrent theory of punishments is of little or no effect in preventing the commission of crimes.

¹⁷ Gavrielides, T, *Restorative Justice Theory and Practice*, 2020, <<https://www.peacepalacelibrary.nl>>.

Utilitarian theory of punishment finds further expression in the reformatory model which focuses on the offender and not his offence and seeks to deal with the root cause of criminality by retraining and reforming the offender. Real-life experience discloses that a good number of criminals make a deliberate choice about a life of crime; their decisions are driven by a cost-benefit analysis. The major problem of this theory is that it shifts responsibility for the actions of the offender from the offender to society. In this regard, the death penalty, though proceeding from a retributive basis also has a utilitarian effect because the murderer is permanently denied the opportunity of committing another homicide. Imprisonment has given rise to a preventive model of punishment with its attendant defect as it occasionally leads to serious injustice. In the face of an imperfect criminal justice system, police misconduct, prosecutorial overzealousness or defence counsel incompetence, acting either singly or in combination, occasionally result in innocent persons being either incarcerated or executed.

Compensatory Theory: Under the Criminal Justice System, the defendant is the sole focus while the victim is useful only in assisting the State to obtain conviction of the offender. Out of all the theories of punishment which include utilitarian and retributive theory which includes *inter alia*, crime victim's compensation is the only theory of penology that considers crime victims' interests. Consequently, while the preceding theories of punishment serve the needs of the society and even that of the offender, they fail to assuage the victim's needs. In 1985, the United Nations General Assembly adopted a declaration on 'Basic Principles of Justice for victims of Crime and Abuse of Power.' Article 9 of the Declaration required governments to review their regulations and laws to consider restitution as a sentencing option in criminal cases in addition to other criminal sanctions.¹⁸

The compensatory theory taken alone, like every other theory of punishment, has severe shortcomings. Since the motive of criminality is not always economic, promotion of economic loss as sufficient punishment for the offender results in the over-simplification of motives for crime. Compensation, as an objective of punishment, finds justification in utilitarianism, so that the primary goal of criminal justice administration ceases being punishment of the offender or

¹⁸ United Nations General Assembly Resolution no 40/34 of 1985.

prevention of commission of further crimes, but rather compensation of the victim. Furthermore, the effect of the punishment depends on the economic status of the offender. Persons of means are less affected by financial loss as punishment than persons with lean resources. In this regard, persons without financial means or property which could be amerced cannot be punished. Taking away the entire economic resources of a person as punishment could leave him with no other means other than resorting to crime for subsistence.

Therapeutic Jurisprudence

Therapeutic jurisprudence believes in recognising, highlighting and exploring the potential for positive and negative impacts upon the victim of crime. This is achieved by repairing the harm caused by criminal behaviour and the enthronement of restorative justice that leads to transformation of the offender, healing of the victim, cohesion of the community and fostering of human relationships.¹⁹

Crime victims differ with regard to what outcome they suffer²⁰ and in order to have a successful crime victim-centred approach, therapeutic jurisprudence needs to be considered on an individual basis.²¹ Additionally, the perception of the crime victims is different from the criminal justice's perception of the outcome. The efficacy of restorative justice is based on the cumulative effect of the shame brought on the perpetrator of the crime and his ultimate restoration of the victim, leading

¹⁹ Balson J. *Therapeutic Jurisprudence: Facilitating Healing in Crime Victims*, Phoenix Law Review 798, 2012 as cited in Matthews, K, Who Tells their Stories?: Examining the Role, Duties, and Ethical Constraints of the Victim's Attorney under Model Rule 3.6 Fordham L. Rev., 2021, <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/flr90&div=41&id=&page=>>.

²⁰ Shimoyachi, N, Between Accountability and Reconciliation: The Making of "the Victim-Centered Approach" at the International Criminal Court, Global Studies Quarterly, 2024 as cited in Tully, LD, The Cultural (Re) Turn: The Case for Teaching Culturally Responsive Lawyering (Stan. JCR & CL, 2020), <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/stjcrcl16&div=10&id=&page=>>.

²¹ Hartley G. and Petrucci A. *Practicing Culturally Competent Therapeutic Jurisprudence: A Collaboration Between Social Work and Law*, Washington University Journal of Law & Policy 111-113, 2004 as cited in Yamada, DC, Therapeutic Jurisprudence: Foundations, Expansion, and Assessment (U. Miami L. Rev., 2020), <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/umialr75&div=21&id=&page=>>.

to his reintegration into society.²² In other words, the acts of restoration will respond to crime by taking steps to repair the harm caused by the crime.

Therapeutic jurisprudence involves all facets of the court system. In essence, whereas the prescriptive character of law and legal systems defines the human being as an object of law, therapeutic jurisprudence defines law as an object for the human being. For instance, rather than cast an offender in the stereotypical perceptions of "wrongdoer," leading to stigmatisation as criminal law would,²³ therapeutic jurisprudence seeks ways of modifying the impact of the conflict by offering a deeper investigation into the behavioural causes and phenomena that gave birth to the perceived wrong.²⁴

The basic elements of therapeutic jurisprudence can lead to a successful healing of the crime victim or any other party affected by the criminal behaviour of the offender. These elements are: apology, forgiveness and reconciliation.²⁵ These elements facilitate conflict resolution between the crime victims and the offenders with a view to providing healing for all the parties affected by the crime. It is trite that common law courts and their presiding functionaries are conferred with a range of discretionary powers in the conduct of proceedings. Many of these powers that originally existed at common law have now become subjects of statutory provisions in Nigeria. For instance, the Criminal Procedure Act (CPA) contains elaborate provisions that have the potential to become platforms for therapeutic criminal justice. While some of such provisions relate to accused persons in general, some exclusively relate to specific groups of offenders, for example, juvenile

²² Braithwaite J. *Restorative Justice: Theories and Worries*, 2004 as cited in Watts, BR & Robertson, K, Impact of Established Restorative Practices in an Urban High-school Environment (Conflict Resolution Quarterly, 2022), Volume 20, Issue 1, pp. 123-140, <<https://doi.org/10.1002/crq.21353>>.

²³ Marder, ID & Wexler DB, Mainstreaming Restorative Justice and Therapeutic Jurisprudence through Higher Education (U. Balt. L. Rev., 2020) <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/ublr50&div=18&id=&page=>>>.

²⁴ McGuire, M, Nation States. Cyberconflict and the Web of Profit, HP Development Company, 2021, <<https://www.hp.com/content/dam/sites/garage-press/press/press-releases/2021/web-of-profit/hp-bps-web-of-profit-report-april-2021.pdf>>.

²⁵ Daicoff W. *Apology Forgiveness Reconciliation & Therapeutic Jurisprudence*, Pepperdine Dispute Resolution Law Journal, 138, 2013 as cited in Yamada, DC, Therapeutic jurisprudence: Foundations, expansion, and assessment, U. Miami L. Rev., 2020, <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/umialr75&div=21&id=&page=>>>.

offenders.²⁶ Section 426 of that Act makes it mandatory for a court to summon the parent or guardian of a juvenile offender who is being arraigned for trial or who is to be sent to an institution, to participate in the proceedings. This provision which would have been a platform for problem-solving, has been honoured more in breach than in observance. Prosecutors, magistrates and judges default on this procedure and defence lawyers, trained only to vanquish the prosecution's case through wits and argumentative delivery, also ignore the procedure.

Effects of Therapeutic Jurisprudence on Nigeria's Criminal Justice System

The effects of therapeutic jurisprudence on Nigeria's criminal justice system are as follows:

- i. ***It Balances the Personal Needs of Victims and Communities with the Broader Goals of Deterring Criminality:*** Therapeutic approach to criminal justice system is an inclusive process, in which all parties directly affected by the behaviour of the offender are involved in discussing its causes and consequences, how to prevent its recurrence and what should happen to the offender. In view of these features, therapeutic approach to criminal justice would fit perfectly in Nigeria as forgiveness, restoration, collaboration, reconciliation and rehabilitation have always been practiced in indigenous Nigerian communities. In this regard, the role of prosecutors and defence lawyers under therapeutic jurisprudence approach in the Nigerian criminal justice system is critical.
- ii. ***Humanises Criminal Justice:*** Therapeutic approach to criminal justice system moves the justice away from retributive practices and injects therapeutic jurisprudence into the criminal justice system in Nigeria where human feeling replaces the desire to punish the offender so as to serve as deterrence to others like-minded individual. The techniques of therapeutic jurisprudence involve the convergence of diverse people who are not part of the conventional training for the operators of criminal justice system. The therapeutic jurisprudence concept has the potential of tempering the effect of erroneous and preconceived notions about litigation being an end in itself,

²⁶ Sections 413-434, Cap C41 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004, S 2(1) of the Act defines a "juvenile offender" as "an offender who has not attained the age of seventeen years".

notions that could have been instilled through the manifest processes of the adversarial justice system.

iii. **Promotes Transformative Alternative:** It is observed that in a country like Nigeria where the retributive operators find it difficult to change from retributive to restorative criminal justice, it will be appropriate for therapeutic approach to be introduced as part of the curriculum of law students so that the law students will grow with it and as they practice law, it would be a form of continuing education for lawyers and judicial officers. The implication, therefore, is that to promote the transformative alternative that therapeutic jurisprudence offers to the adversarial justice system in Nigeria, it becomes critical that the concept be integrated into the curricula of law schools as well as programmes and workshops for lawyers and judicial officers.²⁷

iv. **Reforms Retributive Criminal Justice System:** Over the years, it has been established that penology which is one of the features of retributive criminal justice system, has not in any way reduced the rate of crime in Nigeria, it has toughened the offenders and this has resorted to recidivism. It has even been shown that where penal codes were amended in African common law States, this was often done to increase penalties.²⁸ Punishment has thus remained the dominant feature in the criminal justice system of Nigeria, where judges, magistrates and criminal lawyers in Nigeria would relish their steadfast commitment to the application of the tenets of the English criminal justice system as practised and passed down since colonial times.

Argument for the Return to Restorative Justice

The proponents of restorative justice over the years have argued that the current system of correction which is built on the theory of retributive justice, is unjust to the offender for its systemic

²⁷ Peters, D, *Alternative Dispute Resolution*, Oasis Press, 2nd ed, p.59. 2004, *Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Nigeria: Principles and Practice*, Dee-Sage Nigeria Limited, 2004, as cited in Caleb, OA, *The Nigeria Legal Framework For Arbitration and its Effectiveness in Dispute Resolution*, Open Journal Systems, 2024, <<https://www.nigerianjournalonline.com/index.php/FUNAILAWPROJECTS/article/view/5561>>.

²⁸ Olowu, D, *Therapeutic Jurisprudence: Humanising Criminal Justice in Africa*, 2010, 43(1) De Jure 47-54, 2010.

failure to produce social safety and order.²⁹ It is argued that the prison overcrowding and the inhumane conditions to which prisoners are subjected, the increasing number of prisoner suicides, high rates of reoffending, the rising costs of incapacitation as a policy and philosophy for crime control, the deepening racism and inequality in the secure estate, etc. are some of the reasons that reformists premised their search for restorative justice on. They argued further that a criminal justice system that is based on the concept of retribution that uses punishment inflicted through imprisonment, has failed.³⁰

One of the negative effects of the retributive justice system is that it is the primary way of motivating compliance with the law through the application of sanctions. The consequence of this sanction is that it leads to prison congestion. In view of this, two important failures of the retributive system are cited by proponents of restorative justice: the programmatic effect of failure to address the rights of victims to redress and the failure of the punitive approach to crime to produce effective deterrence.³¹ The most important argument for restorative justice is the abandonment of victims' interests by the jurisprudence of retribution.

However, it is important to note that the adoption of the system of retributive justice replaced an earlier tribal system of compensatory justice³² that is being put forth as a new philosophy for modern societies, which has its roots in the older traditions in non-modern societies. In the contemporary period, there is a concerted call to replace the established system of retributive

²⁹ Theo Gavrielides, *Reconciling the Notions of Restorative Justice and Imprisonment*, 94 *The Prison Journal*, 479–480, 2014 as cited in Ross, K and Muro D, Possibilities of Prison-based Restorative Justice: Transformation beyond Recidivism, *Contemporary Justice Review*, 2020, Volume 23, Issue, 3, pp. 291-313, <<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10282580.2020.1783258>>.

³⁰ Mauer, M & Coyle, M, *The Social Cost of America's Race to Incarcerate*, in Eleanor Hannon Judah & Michal Bryant, *Criminal Justice: Retribution vs. Restoration*, (2nd ed), 21 Haworth Press, 2004 as cited in Morrison, M, The Mass Incarceration Trauma Framework: A Conceptual Model For Understanding Trauma Among Individuals Who Experience Incarceration *Social work*, 2024, Volume 69, Issue 1, pp, 8–16, <<https://doi.org/10.1093/sw/swad040>>.

³¹ Strong, H & Sherman, L, *Repairing the Harm: Victims and Restorative Justice*, 15 *UTAH L. REV.* 15, 2003 as cited in Anderson, A, A Pleasure to Burn: How First Amendment Jurisprudence on Book Banning Bolsters White Supremacy, *Mitchell Hamline L. Rev.*, 2023, <<https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/wmitch49&div=4&id=&page=>>>.

³² Garvey, S, *Restorative Justice, Punishment, and Atonement*, 1 *UTAH L. REV.* 304, 2003 as cited in Altman, M, A Theory of Legal Punishment: Deterrence, Retribution, and the Aims of the State, London, Routledge, 2021, <<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003143>>.

justice, which focuses on the state imposing punishment, with a “new” system of restorative justice.

Conclusion

The conventional retributive justice in Nigeria does not only focus upon the state being the victim and places the individual victim in a passive position with little participation in the justice process, the jurisprudence of the new paradigm shift is based on compensation to the victim while the offender is actively involved in resolving the aftermath of the offence committed by him/her. While the State is an active participant under the retributive justice system, the reverse is the case under the jurisprudence of restorative justice theory, which makes the State be a passive participant, or at most a party facilitating the interaction of victim and offender. The Nigerian criminal justice system should see resolution of crime from a restorative lens that treats the new paradigm of restorative justice as a violation of one person by another, not a violation of the state, with a focus upon problem-solving for the future rather than establishing blame for past behaviour. Rather than the imposition of severe punishment, the Nigerian legal jurisprudence of restorative justice should emphasise restitution as a means of restoring and reconciling both parties as its goals. Instead of ignoring the victims and placing offenders in a passive role, the new paradigm of restorative justice jurisprudence in Nigeria should place both victim and offender in active and interpersonal problem-solving roles.

Interestingly, most jurisdictions of the world are moving towards enthrone restorative justice in the administration of the criminal justice system, and Nigeria should not be left behind in this laudable cause. While restorative justice to the victim of crime is being witnessed in the United States, the Commonwealth States of Australia, New Zealand, Canada and Pakistan, it is yet to be given serious attention in Nigeria by making it part and parcel of the criminal justice system in Nigeria. As regards restorative justice for the victim of crime, Nigeria still has many miles to travel. If adversarial criminal justice has thus undergone so much transformation in England, such that the notions of retribution and deterrence are no longer prioritised, why should courts and lawyers in Nigeria continue to live in the past?

Recommendations

Though in Nigeria's jurisprudence, there are compensation, restitution and restoration that remain a clear-cut policy which should be preferred above imprisonment and other punishments, it was found that there is a dearth of restorative justice aimed at restoring the victims of economic and financial crime to their *status quo ante*. The principal statutes prohibiting criminal acts in general, to wit: the Criminal Code Act and the Penal Code Act, focus mainly on punishing the perpetrators of the crime. There should be regular revision and review of our laws generally to take care of new developments and situations. The two principal statutes should be reviewed and amended to make provisions for the recovery of scammed fund and return same to the victims of such fraud or criminality. The provision of section 14(2) of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) Act regarding compensation is salutary while that of Section 270 of the Administration of Criminal Justice Act regarding plea bargain should be reviewed to be directly beneficial to the victims of crime and not only to the government. A similar provision to section 14(2) of the EFCC Act should be introduced in both the Criminal Code Act and the Penal Code Act, which are the principal laws that define and penalise criminal conduct.